

Perturbation Effects on Compression of a Plasma Target in Cylindrical Geometry

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Using numerical simulations, we investigate the influence of perturbations on the compression of a plasma target (here, a DT cylinder) by a plasma liner (here, a Kr cylindrical shell). Although the present work is done in cylindrical geometry, future application includes spherical geometries including plasma-jet-driven magneto-inertial fusion (PJMIF). The primary goal of this document is to present progress in determining what is “good enough” liner uniformity for target compression.

We compare results from the HELIOS code (<http://www.prism-cs.com/Software/Helios/overview.html>) and FLASH code (<http://flash.uchicago.edu/site/index.shtml>). HELIOS is 1D Lagrangian. FLASH is 1D, 2D, or 3D Eulerian. For now, we apply no radiation transport and no magnetic fields. We use Spitzer conductivity, and equation of state data is from PROPACEOS (see <http://www.prism-cs.com/Software/Propaceos/overview.html>). For the FLASH 3D case, we use a quasi-2D cylindrical geometry, where the z-coordinate is negligible in 3D, and we take a 60 degree wedge in the theta direction. For these 3D results, our radial resolution is 43.4 μm , and our theta resolution is 3.75 degrees.

We observe more numerical diffusion using the FLASH code (Eulerian) compared with HELIOS (Lagrangian). For moderate convergence ratios of the target (here, $\text{CR} = 4 \text{ cm} / r(t) \sim 8$ at $t = 500 \text{ ns}$), FLASH and HELIOS agree reasonably well. For reference, the desired CR for PJMIF is 10 to 15. Density perturbations influence the liner ram pressure, and this nonuniformity decreases the obtained target temperature. Immediate next steps will look at different plasma parameters (e.g. liner density).

Near-term future work using FLASH will implement radiation, a thermal conductivity multiplier (as a stand-in for a magnetic field and anisotropic conduction), and different perturbations (different azimuthal mode numbers, amplitudes, sinusoidal vs. spikes, etc.). Longer-term future work using FLASH will apply a non-zero magnetic field, use anisotropic thermal conductivity rather than a global conductivity multiplier, and explore spherical geometry (in 2D and/or 3D).

Table I. Initial Conditions

Parameter	Target	Liner
Radius	0 to 4 cm	4 to 5 cm
Material	DT (50% D, 50% T)	Kr
Velocity	0 km/s	70 km/s (radially inward)
Mass Density	1E-5 g/cc	0.03 g/cc (*and perturbations)
Temperature	100 eV	1.5 eV (*and perturbations)

Comparisons of HELIOS (1D), 1D FLASH, and 3D FLASH (quasi-2D)
400 ns (CR ~4)

500 ns (CR ~8)

600 ns (CR ~80)

Liner Perturbations Setup

Density ("3D" FLASH wedge) with no liner perturbations

Density ("3D" FLASH wedge) with 50% sinusoidal perturbations

Temperature ("3D" FLASH wedge) with no liner perturbations

Temperature ("3D" FLASH wedge) with 50% sinusoidal perturbations

Perturbation effects (all with 3D FLASH wedge)

Radial lineouts taken 1) along theta location of **perturbation maximum**, and 2) **averaged** over all theta

400 ns (CR ~4)

500 ns (CR ~8)

600 ns (CR ~80)

